

1 **Alternative mode of nucleotide synthesis in resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC.**

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7 TYMP was activated concomitant with TYMS repression.

8 Citations

9 1. Jividen, R., Yue, H. and Li, W., 2024. Thymidine phosphorylase plays a mechanistic role in lipid
10 metabolism and obesity. *Circulation*, 150(Suppl_1), pp.A4144892-A4144892.
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